

Perspective-Shift Attacks Against Optical Perception Sensors: A Novel Attack Vector on LiDAR and Camera

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Abstract

Autonomous vehicles rely heavily on optical perception sensors, such as LiDARs and cameras, to understand their environment. Both sensors have been the subject of study in the automotive security community, with attacks ranging from physical hijacking, by introducing adversarial stimuli within the sensing range, denoted as the field of view, to crafting specialized adversarial objects designed to fool the underlying machine learning model in tasks such as object detection. This paper introduces a novel class of physical attacks, namely Perspective Shift Attacks, that aim to manipulate the sensors' field of view to induce dangerous driving maneuvers in life-critical scenarios. We show that using Direction Turning Film, an optical material that bends light by a predefined angle, can adversarially alter the field of view of optical perception sensors. Unlike prior attacks that inject adversarial signals or modify the environment, our approach stealthily alters the perceived sensing region without significantly degrading detection confidence performance. We present a digital simulation framework and validate the attack through controlled laboratory experiments and real-world deployments on a real autonomous driving research vehicle. Results show that even moderate field-of-view shifts of 20° significantly impact critical tasks, including LiDAR-based odometry and camera-based lane detection, potentially triggering dangerous maneuvers, such as unintentionally invading the opposite lane, while having only a minor effect on the confidence of object detection algorithms, despite altering object positions. Finally, we propose detection mechanisms that leverage physical-layer artifacts and semantic consistency checks to mitigate perspective-shift attacks. Our findings reveal perspective-shift attacks as an unexplored and practical attack surface, underscoring the need for robust sensor security in autonomous vehicles.

Figure 1: Perspective-Shift Attacks induce a shift in the FoV of Optical Perception Sensors without causing a noticeable degradation in the performance of tasks such as object detection. As a result, the AV cannot detect the attack, which may lead to unsafe behavior in safety-critical scenarios due to incorrect decision-making. For instance, the vehicle fails to accurately estimate its trajectory or street lanes.

1 Introduction

Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) have become a reality [40, 54]. A key enabler of this progress is the perception sensor suite, which allows an AV to gather information from its environment and forward it to subsequent processing modules. Among perception sensors, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDARs) and cameras have received considerable attention in the context of autonomous vehicle security [1], leading to the identification of multiple attack categories targeting these sensors [29, 51].

Within these categories, physical attacks have been proposed with the aim of disrupting system behavior. Most existing attacks focus on impairing the functionality of the AV ei-

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ther by directly targeting the sensors themselves, e.g., through blinding attacks [44], or by targeting the underlying Machine Learning (ML) models via the introduction of artifacts into sensor data [13, 58]. Such artifacts are typically introduced using adversarial objects, such as patches or stickers, placed in the environment [13, 24, 35]. Consequently, an alternative and largely unexplored direction is to affect AV functionality by deliberately altering the sensor’s perceived sensing region, namely its Field Of View (FoV).

The FoV is an inherent characteristic of every Optical Perception Sensor (OPS), and no prior physical attack has explicitly targeted shifting it. By deliberately altering the sensing region, it is possible to introduce a perspective shift that changes the area in which perception algorithms operate, without degrading their performance. This contrasts with existing physical attacks, in which the FoV remains unchanged, and the attack aims to perturb sensor measurements within it. By contrast, simply shifting the sensor’s perspective can elicit unintended behaviors. We refer to this new attack vector as a *Perspective-Shift Attack (PSA)*. To achieve this PSA, we investigate optical films as a class of materials capable of modifying the angle of incoming light [36], shaping light into specific shapes [38], or increasing perceived brightness [37]. In contrast to attacks based on translucent patches [64] or stickers [13], PSAs do not aim to directly induce misdetections or misclassifications. Instead, the goal is to shift the sensor’s optical perspective in a way that covertly manipulates the spatial perception of the environment, thereby misleading other driving functions and leading to hazardous, potentially safety-critical decisions.

To instantiate our optical film-based PSA, we employ Direction Turning Film (DTF) [36], which bends incoming light by a predefined angle. Depending on the material properties, this light-bending effect can be achieved with varying deflection magnitudes [4]. As this manipulation affects all subsequent processing modules in the autonomous driving pipeline, we evaluate its impact on multiple representative algorithms, including odometry estimation, lane detection, and object detection. Using digital simulations, we first assess the effect of adversarial FoV changes on both LiDAR and camera sensors. We then conduct extensive real-world evaluations in laboratory environments and on real vehicles, targeting individual sensors and demonstrating a multi-modal attack. Based on these evaluations, we further derive detection mechanisms to protect LiDARs and cameras against PSAs.

In summary, we make the following contributions:

- **Identify PSAs as an attack vector against optical perception sensors:** We present a class of physical attacks that deliberately alter the perceived FoV of OPSs, and refer to them as PSAs. In contrast to prior attacks, we do not aim to attack the sensors [44] or underlying ML models by placing adversarial patches [13, 55] or introducing additional objects [27]. Instead, our goal is not to degrade perception performance, but to cause a con-

trolled shift in the perceived FoV. We demonstrate this effect using DTF, an optical film that deflects light by a predefined angle.

- **Evaluate the effect of PSAs:** We present a digital simulation to investigate the effect of an altered FoV on the sensor data. Specifically, we show the effect for lane detection and odometry estimation algorithms. We provide our simulation and measurement data as an open-source code¹.
- **Real-world evaluation of our DTF-based PSA:** To validate the attack in the real world, we evaluate the impact of a shift in perspective in real vehicles, individually for LiDAR and camera, as well as from a multimodal setting, where we show the effect of coherently applied PSA.
- **Detect PSAs:** We propose two methods to detect FoV changes, one for LiDARs and one for cameras. Our methods analyze the sensed data and do not require any change to the hardware setup.

2 Background

This section provides background on existing physical adversarial attacks, the DTF material, the FoV of OPSs, and odometry estimation and lane-detection algorithms.

2.1 Physical Attacks on Autonomous Vehicles

Due to the high number of environmental sensors used in AVs, they are vulnerable not only to digital attacks known from connected vehicles but also to physical attacks that tamper with sensor input [43], leading to unexpected behavior and potentially safety-critical maneuvers. Previous studies have shown that especially perception sensors, such as cameras and LiDAR sensors, are vulnerable to such physical attacks [11, 16, 18]. As shown in Table 1, the majority of well-known physical attacks aims to disrupt the performance of a specific algorithm within the AV stack, targeting perception algorithms to hide, alter, or create objects in the object detection algorithms [13, 19, 34, 35, 55, 62, 63]. Highly specialized attacks, such as [8, 42], target subsequent stages of the multi-stage pipeline of AVs [56], focusing on algorithms such as Simultaneous Location And Mapping (SLAM). The high degree of specialization required for these attacks to be successful categorizes them as non-function-agnostic attacks, because the attack-crafting mechanism is tailored to the internals of the targeted algorithm. Moreover, they targeted a single sensor, either camera or LiDAR, and they have not transferred the specific attack to multi-sensor scenarios. On

¹<https://github.com/tum-esi/PSA>

Table 1: Comparison of existing physical attacks against OPSs on AVs with our proposed DTF-based.

Attack	Multi-Sensor	Stealth	Phys. Access to Victim	Function-Agnostic	Selectable Victim
Eykholt <i>et al.</i> [13]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Zhu <i>et al.</i> [62]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
Lovisotto <i>et al.</i> [35]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Liu <i>et al.</i> [34]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
Zhu <i>et al.</i> [63]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Cao <i>et al.</i> [5]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
Kobayashi <i>et al.</i> [27]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Chen <i>et al.</i> [8]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Cao <i>et al.</i> [42]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Zolfi <i>et al.</i> [64]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
Li <i>et al.</i> [31]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
Zhou <i>et al.</i> [61]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
Ours	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

the other hand, [31, 61, 64] require physical access to the victim to deploy the attack, because they expect to place either a translucent patch or a lens in front of the victim’s sensor. In terms of human stealthiness, namely those attacks that are not visible to human eyes, many of the works we researched lack this property [6, 8, 13, 27, 35, 63, 64]. Finally, the possibility of having a selectable victim allows for attacking a specific vehicle rather than affecting all passing vehicles. This is different from works such as [6, 8, 13, 27], where the attack medium is deployed in the environment and potentially affects all the passing AVs.

As shown in Table 1, our PSA distinguishes itself from the existing approaches by being effective in a multi-sensor setup with LiDARs and cameras, stealthy to humans, and function-agnostic against selectable victims with only one-time physical access.

2.2 Direction Turning Film

DTF is a film used mainly for illumination applications, specifically for wall-washing or for avionic displays, where the viewing angle needs to be adjusted to ensure visibility [36]. These applications exploit the material’s bending property, i.e., collimated light passing through an optic at a specific angle. Such an effect is possible due to the material’s design, which features asymmetric microprisms embedded directly within a polycarbonate sheet, allowing it to bend the outgoing light. The behaviour of the material can be characterized via Snell’s law of refraction [25], which describes the interaction of electromagnetic waves at the interface of two materials with different refractive indices.

2.3 Optical Perception Sensors in Autonomous Vehicles

OPSs are a class of sensors used in AVs to perceive the environment in which the vehicle operates. This category includes

sensors such as LiDARs and cameras. Because these sensors rely on optical elements, their perception of the environment ϵ is inherently constrained by their optics and physical design. We define the environment ϵ as the physical scene observable by an OPS at a given time and location. As a result, each OPS observes only a limited portion of the surrounding area in the horizontal and vertical directions, referred to as the FoV, adapted from the SAE-J1050 standard [9]. The FoV of an OPS is then defined as the tuple of these angular intervals as shown in Equation 1.

$$\text{FoV}_{\text{OPS}} := (H_{\text{FoV}}, V_{\text{FoV}}) \quad (1)$$

The horizontal (H_{FoV}) and vertical FoV (V_{FoV}), as shown in Equation 2, are constrained by the technical specification of the respective OPS.

$$H_{\text{FoV}} = [\theta_{\min}, \theta_{\max}], \quad V_{\text{FoV}} = [\phi_{\min}, \phi_{\max}] \quad (2)$$

While ϵ is unbounded in principle, the sensor’s optical and physical constraints restrict observation to a finite subset $\epsilon^* \subset \epsilon$. It is defined in Equation 3, where $\theta(p)$ and $\phi(p)$ denote the azimuth θ and elevation ϕ of a point p expressed in the sensor reference frame.

$$\epsilon^* = \{p \in \epsilon \mid \theta(p) \in H_{\text{FoV}} \wedge \phi(p) \in V_{\text{FoV}}\} \quad (3)$$

Finally, the output x of an OPS operating in environment ϵ is modeled in Equation 4, where \mathcal{S} denotes the sensing function that maps the observable portion of the environment ϵ^* to the sensor’s measurement space.

$$x = \mathcal{S}(\epsilon^*) \quad (4)$$

2.4 ICP-Based LiDAR Odometry

Iterative Closest Point (ICP) based odometry allows AVs to achieve precise pose estimation via processing consecutive LiDAR point clouds, without relying directly on feature extraction [60]. Being agnostic to features allows ICP based methods to perform better in environments where features are sparser or less present, relying additionally on the geometry of the LiDAR scans. The core idea behind ICP based odometry is to iteratively compute a transformation matrix that minimizes the point-to-point distance among successive scans. A representative example of ICP based odometry is Keep It Small and Simple - Iterative Closest Point (KISS-ICP) [52], which presents a pipeline that works across different domains and LiDAR models with a single set of parameters, making it the reference for odometry estimation in the scientific literature.

2.5 Lane Detection

Lane detection is an important perception task in AVs, and its results are typically used for subsequent tasks like correct

lane keeping [59]. In order to function correctly, an AV needs to derive its position within the lane [41]. By changing the FoV, this estimation can be disrupted. Many lane detection ML models, such as HybridNets [53], provide both detected lanes and the drivable area. The result will be a segmentation map that classifies the pixel positions in an image as either a lane or a street.

3 Threat Model

In the following sections, we will introduce the threat model used throughout the remainder of this paper and the attacker’s knowledge and capabilities.

3.1 Attack Goal and Characteristics

The goal of our PSA is to change the FoV of an OPS, specifically targeting LiDAR sensors and cameras. In contrast to existing attacks [13, 19, 34, 35, 55, 62, 63], PSAs do not aim to hide, alter, or create objects in the sensor data by changing the environment ϵ but rather change the FoV of the targeted sensor, thus leading to wrongly derived positions of objects. This is possible by the introduction of an angular shift Δ_{PSA} which is positive when the shift is applied to the left in the horizontal plane or upward in the vertical plane, and negative for the opposite directions.

Practically, this translates into the FoV by adapting Equation 2 into Equation 5 for a horizontal shift, and into Equation 6 for a vertical shift. It is important to note that only one of these shifts can be applied at a time.

$$H_{\text{FoV,PSA}} = [\theta_{\min} + \Delta_{\text{PSA}}, \theta_{\max} + \Delta_{\text{PSA}}] \quad (5)$$

$$V_{\text{FoV,PSA}} = [\phi_{\min} + \Delta_{\text{PSA}}, \phi_{\max} + \Delta_{\text{PSA}}] \quad (6)$$

This alters the subset of perceived points ϵ^* described in Equation 3, and consequently the sensor output x from Equation 4.

The primary characteristic of our attack is that the shift Δ_{PSA} is not induced by mechanical manipulation of the sensor, such as physically rotating it, but rather by light deflection through an optical film, specifically DTF. Consequently, the applied DTF causes the sensor to perceive the environment as if it were being rotated, forcing the AV to compensate for the rotation, and causing safety-critical situations.

Our DTF-based PSA can be characterized as follows:

- **Stealthiness:** An important characteristic of our attack is the stealthiness of the transparent patch against humans. This is achieved by using transparent DTF, which involves adding only a transparent, inconspicuous film to the OPS, with a minimum size required to fully cover the respective sensor.
- **Limited Physical Access:** Once the DTF is placed on the OPS of the target vehicle, no further physical access is needed.

- **Controlled Target:** While adversarial patches on remote objects, such as traffic signs [13], might affect multiple or even unintended assets, our attack is directly deployed on the intended target, allowing the attacker to specifically control a selected target.
- **Minor Adversarial Impact on Perception:** PSAs change the FoV of an OPS with ideally no impact on the detection or classification performance of the perception models used in the respective data processing. While introducing a film on the sensor will create some optical artifacts or noise, this is only a side effect with very limited impact on the perception modules.
- **Multi-Modal Attack:** Our attack is effective both against LiDAR sensors and cameras, making it effective for systems that use sensor fusion.
- **Independent of Illumination:** Many attacks are known to work only in specific illumination conditions [3, 10, 15]. By contrast, our attack is effective independently of the environmental illumination.

3.2 Attacker Knowledge and Capabilities

We assume an attack with **no prior knowledge of the perception modules** used in an AV ("black-box attack"). This includes details of the ML model weights, architecture, and the stages within the perception module, and distinguishes our attack from similar attacks that apply patches to cameras [31].

As highlighted in our attack characteristics, the attacker requires **one-time physical access to the target vehicle** to place the DTF on the respective OPS. This is similar to other attacks that apply patches on the cameras [17, 31, 50, 64].

An attacker needs to **have minimum system knowledge** of the targeted AV, specifically the positions of the OPSs. Such knowledge can be obtained through visual inspection of the target vehicle or public sources of reference vehicles. We emphasize that only the sensor positions are required, without any further technical details.

Lastly, for our DTF-based PSA, an attacker needs to have **enough DTF to cover the respective sensor area**, which is typically limited to a relatively small area. Depending on the desired bending angle, specific DTF material is required. For our attack deployment, we will use a material which introduces an offset of 20° [36].

4 Digital Attack Simulation

We create a digital simulation of our DTF-based PSA that operates on pre-captured real data to simulate the effect of the FoV shift on specific tasks for the targeted OPSs.

Figure 2: Representative frames from the digital simulation with a simulated 20° PSA. The top row shows LiDAR scans from the KITTI Odometry benchmark, while the bottom row presents the camera views from a real-world driving scenario.

4.1 Digital Simulation

The perspective shift of our DTF-based PSA depends on the material properties and cannot be changed by the attacker after deployment. The magnitude and direction of the shift, however, can be chosen so that an attacker can deploy the DTF to shift the perceived sensor data up, down, left, or right, by applying a different film. In our simulation, we use a perspective shift of 20° , as this is physically realizable with commercially available DTF [36]. However, the effect of other shifts can be simulated with our tool.

To simulate the FoV shift at the LiDAR, we digitally modify the KITTI odometry dataset [14], which allows for the dynamic adjustment of the FoV in conjunction with the description of OPS provided in Equation 4. As a result, it is possible to create custom sequences from the KITTI odometry to be fed to any algorithm, as shown in Figures 2a-2c.

For the camera, our simulation uses a dual-fisheye representation of spherical images, as is often captured by omnidirectional cameras. Based on a freely selectable center point, our simulation creates a curvilinear projection of a specified FoV. This projection mimics the FoV of a camera in an environment \mathcal{E} , represented by the spherical image. Figures 2d-2f depict the benign image in the center and both simulated directions of the FoV. Although not depicted, the upward and downward shifts can also be simulated.

4.2 Digital Evaluation

For both sensors, we evaluate the impact of the attack on left- and right-shifted sensor data, as these shifts are more interesting to attackers than up- and downward shifts, since they

can lead to misbehavior, such as incorrect steering commands. As representative AV algorithms, we use a KISS-ICP-based odometry estimation [52] and evaluate its relative displacement for the LiDAR, and HybridNets [53] for lane detection and its displacement in cameras.

4.2.1 LiDAR

As previously described, we evaluate the PSA-induced relative displacement, using the KITTI odometry dataset [14]. Figure 3 shows the comparison of the effect of a shifted FoV. In our digital evaluation, we consider a Horizontal FoV of 150° oriented in the vehicle's driving direction in the KITTI odometry dataset, in line with the specifics of commercially available LiDARs, and the vertical FoV remains untouched. As per the displacement, we consider 20° in both the right and left directions.

It is worth noticing that the displacement is not computed with respect to the KITTI Ground Truth (GT), but relative to a reference run executed without any shift for the specific FoV under analysis. This approach enables the evaluation of displacement while avoiding the bias introduced by cropping the original point cloud. The evaluation is conducted on all KITTI odometry sequences that provide a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) GT to compensate for possible noise introduced by the algorithm. The results reported in Figure 3 show the average displacement for each sequence. The KISS-ICP employs a robust optimization strategy to mitigate potential errors in pose estimation. Specifically, the registration process enforces temporal consistency by incorporating prior pose estimates, particularly the two preceding poses. The results indicate that sequences with larger average dis-

Figure 3: Result of a run of the LiDAR digital simulation. We reported the measured displacement, in meters, of the ΔX coordinate of the estimated pose relative to the benchmark reference towards the KITTI driving direction.

placements generally correspond to turning maneuvers (e.g., sequences 00, 01, and 02). In contrast, in sequences where the vehicle follows a predominantly straight trajectory (e.g., 03 and 04), the average displacement remains negligible. This behavior can be attributed to the fact that, when the FoV is sufficiently wide and the applied shift is moderate, the extracted features remain largely consistent, resulting in limited degradation of the pose estimate. Conversely, during turning maneuvers, the shift has a more pronounced impact on the registration process, leading to significantly corrupted pose estimates.

4.2.2 Camera

We use the street scenery from Figures 2d to 2f, captured with a dual-fisheye camera as a ground-truth for our digital simulation, and perform a HybridNets-based lane detection [53]. Figure 4b shows the benign lane detection, while Figures 4a and 4c depict the simulated left- and right shift by 20° , introduced by the PSA. The individual lines are color-separated to differentiate them. While the detected lanes are qualitatively similar, they have different positions that can result in incorrect steering commands, since functionality like lane departure warnings and other lane-related tasks do not compensate for a changing FoV but assume a fixed mounted sensor for their control algorithms [2, 41]. The left shift of Figure 4a results in a right shift of the vanishing point, and the right shift in Figure 4c leads to a left shift of the vanishing point. In both cases, the vanishing point is not at the optical center anymore, as in the benign case of Figure 4b. As our simulation considers the camera-specific FoV, an attacker can evaluate the necessary direction of the PSA to perform a successful attack, such as removing neighboring lines.

5 Experiments

We evaluate our DTF-based PSA against LiDAR and camera sensors, both in static and real-world tests.

5.1 Overview

In our initial overview, we will define our setup, the attack success metrics, and the targeted algorithms.

5.1.1 Hardware Setup

For the real-world deployment of our PSA, we use a DTF that introduces an offset of 20° [36]. We apply the DTF to create both left and right shifts as they are especially interesting in the use case of autonomous driving. We test different LiDAR and camera sensors to show the system-agnostic effects of the attack. The exact sensing hardware used is specified within each evaluation use case. Lastly, we evaluate both LiDAR and camera individually, as well as in a common setup within an autonomous driving research vehicle [26].

5.1.2 Attack Success & Targeted Algorithms

For the LiDAR-based system, we measure the attack impact using the *relative displacement of the odometry estimation*, expressed in meters, of the estimated pose along the axis orthogonal to the vehicle’s driving direction (i.e., the lateral axis). LiDAR odometry is essential for AVs, providing accurate localization by estimating the vehicle’s position through scan alignment, and serving as a foundation for trajectory estimation [32] and SLAM [20]. To evaluate the effect of our attack, we focus on the KISS-ICP algorithm [52], a state-of-the-art ICP-based method ideally suited for laser scan-based odometry. The relative displacement is directly motivated by the effect of PSAs on the LiDAR sensor. Each point of a LiDAR’s point cloud p_i can be expressed in spherical coordinates (r_i, θ_i, ϕ_k) , where r_i is the distance of the point in space, θ_i is the azimuth angle (horizontal angle), and ϕ_k is the elevation, set by the disposition of the k -th laser array (vertical angle). When applied to the sensor’s optics, PSAs introduces a horizontal shift Δ_{PSA} in the sensor’s horizontal FoV, which translates in Cartesian coordinates as a rotation of the forward-lateral plane around the vertical axis. Empirical evaluation showed that the coordinate most affected by the attack is the lateral axis, and for this reason, we deem the attacks successful for the LiDAR if the average displacement is greater than 1m, which corresponds to scenarios where a dangerous maneuver might happen, such as entering the opposite lane.

For the camera, we demonstrate the PSA effect on lane detection by investigating the *vanishing-point displacement*. Lane detection is an important functionality for AVs and advanced driver assistance systems. Because they can capture color images, cameras are typically used for lane detection tasks [21, 59]. We will use HybridNets [53] as a representative lane detection algorithm. For straight lanes and a centrally mounted front-facing camera, the vanishing point is located at the optical center of the image; however, it shifts with a PSA. We quantify this effect by calculating the horizontal

Figure 4: Detected, color-separated lanes for the digitally simulated PSA. The central image shows the benign FoV. While the attacked images still contain all lanes, their coordinates differ significantly.

offset of the vanishing point from the optical center in pixels. As the pinhole camera model is accurate enough for most cameras [48], we can also derive the bending angle of our DTF-based PSA, as demonstrated in our static physical tests.

In parallel, we utilize object detection algorithms to showcase that PSAs have only minor adverse impact on perceived object appearance. For the cameras, we select the generic Faster R-CNN [45] object detector as well as a specifically trained version of YOLOv10 [28] to detect objects. For the object detection with the LiDAR, we use PointPillars [30], and SECOND [57] pretrained on the KITTI dataset [14]. To demonstrate that detection of smaller objects remains possible, we use YOLOv10, trained on the Mapillary traffic sign dataset [12, 28], for camera-based traffic sign detection. Since the attacked data has an offset in the FoV, they will *not* contain the same objects or the same number of objects as the benign data. Typical metrics, such as mean average precision, will therefore not provide valid results. As a solution, we use the *average confidence of detected objects* of the same type in all captured scenes for both scenarios to investigate the impact on the perception.

5.2 Static Physical Tests

To assess the effectiveness of PSAs against OPSs in a real environment, we conducted static physical tests with a DTF. The goal of the tests is to observe and quantify the optical shift caused by the DTF when applied to the sensor’s optics. To do so, for both LiDAR and camera, we use a reference object posed precisely in front of the sensor, aligned with the optical center axis. The first set of measurements is carried out without any perspective shift, whereas the second set of measurements is carried out with DTF-induced perspective shift. The experiment is evaluated based on the shift perceived by the OPS of the reference objects. This test enables us to confirm our assumptions about the effectiveness of the attack in a controlled scenario, with minimal external noise sources.

5.2.1 LiDAR

For the LiDAR, we use an object that is highly distinguishable within the surrounding environment. As traffic signs are retroreflective, resulting in a high intensity value perceived by the LiDAR, we use them to evaluate the FoV shift by measuring the change in azimuth of the highest reflectivity peak [39]. This, combined with a plain wooden background, is the identification of the traffic sign in the perceived data.

Figure 5c shows the result of the test using an Ouster OS1 64 [22], where the reference scene is depicted in blue, and the adversarial case in red. Within the reference polar plot, it is evident that the highest reflectivity values are centered at 0° , indicating the location where the traffic sign is placed. If we now observe the same peak in the attack line, we can see that it is shifted by approximately half of the first circumference sector, confirming a shift of 20° , which is coherent with the description of the DTF we employed for the test. It is worth noting that some of the optical aberrations in the adversarial point cloud are due to the rounded surfaces of the sensor’s optics. As we will investigate in Subsection 5.3.1, they have a negligible effect on the final perception algorithms. Moreover, since a left shift of the FoV yields qualitatively the same effect, only mirrored in the opposite direction, Figure 5 shows only the right-shifted data for clarity.

5.2.2 Camera

We project a reference image with vertical lines at 10° intervals in a static indoor setup, capturing images with a Sony ILCE-6400 [46]. Figure 6 depicts these images, with the red line at the center marking the 0° position.

With the knowledge of camera parameters, namely the physical image sensor width w in mm, the focal length f in mm, and the image width x_I in pixels, we can calculate the horizontal angle θ of a specific pixel $p_{x,y}$ as an offset from the center. Since the pinhole camera model is sufficiently accurate for our application [48], and w , f , and x_I are static parameters for a captured image, θ only depends on the horizontal pixel

Figure 5: Figure 5c shows the reflectivity peak under attack (Figure 5b, red) at $\approx 20^\circ$, compared to the benign case (Figure 5a, dotted blue). This confirms that real LiDAR systems are affected by the PSA.

Figure 6: Reference images with vertical lines at each 10° . The central image shows the benign FoV, while the outer images show the FoV with the PSA. The central red reference line has a relative offset of 0.02° in the benign image, and -19.42° and $+19.40^\circ$ in the respective adversarial images.

position p_x , as shown in Equation 7:

$$\theta(p_x) = \frac{\arctan\left(\frac{w}{2f}\right)(2p_x - x_l)}{x_l} \quad (7)$$

Applying this to the red reference line in the images of Figure 6 results in $\theta(p_{x,\text{benign}}) = 0.02^\circ$ for the benign case of Figure 6b. The left shift in Figure 6a results in $\theta(p_{x,\text{left}}) = 19.40^\circ$, and the right shift of Figure 6c results in $\theta(p_{x,\text{right}}) = -19.42^\circ$. These measurements confirm the practical applicability of the DTF for PSAs in a static scenario. We will investigate the effect of possible artifacts from the DTF with object detection models in our following real-world tests.

5.3 Real-World Tests

We categorize our real-world tests into three categories to evaluate PSAs against both LiDAR and a camera, individually and in a multimodal setup. Data are collected using an autonomous driving research vehicle [26] operating under natural urban traffic conditions. Experiments are conducted at variable vehicle speeds ranging from 10 to 50km/h, consistent with local urban traffic regulations. Throughout all trials, the DTF remains securely attached to the sensor, demonstrating the physical plausibility and robustness of the proposed attack under realistic deployment conditions.

5.3.1 LiDAR

We evaluate the real-world impact of the proposed PSA by deploying the DTF directly on the optical aperture of an Innovision Falcon Gen2 LiDAR [49] sensor, as shown in Figure 7a, which features a horizontal FoV of 120° . To quantify the effect of the induced FoV displacement, we compare the trajectory estimated via KISS-ICP against the GT trajectory obtained from high-precision GNSS pose measurements. The DTF is mounted directly in front of the LiDAR optics and secured using tape, ensuring both mechanical stability and visual stealthiness. This mounting approach enables a robust attachment under both low- and high-speed driving conditions, without compromising the sensor’s operational integrity.

As illustrated in Figure 8, the trajectory estimated by KISS-ICP exhibits a clear and systematic deviation from the GNSS ground truth, confirming the effectiveness of the induced perturbation. Moreover, the observed distortion in the recorded point clouds is consistent with both our prior controlled experiments and the initial digital simulations, manifesting as a measurable displacement in the estimated pose coordinates attributable to the applied DTF. These results provide strong evidence that the proposed PSAs are effective in transferring from simulation to real-world driving scenarios, underscoring their practical feasibility and potential real-world impact.

For the LiDAR-based object detection, we use Pointpil-

(a) DTF deployed on a real vehicle LiDAR

(b) DTF deployed on a front-facing camera

Figure 7: Examples of the DTF deployed on LiDAR and camera of real vehicles

Figure 8: Plot of the estimated odometry using the LiDAR with the DTF deployed against the GNSS system present on the autonomous vehicle. The plot highlights that a 20° offset over an FoV of 120° highly impacts the estimated poses, deeming our attack on the LiDAR a success, with a displacement of the poses in the orthogonal driving direction (y axis in the innovation coordinate system) of 100m.

lars [30], and SECOND [57] on both benign and attacked point cloud sequences. We set the detection confidence threshold to 0.6 for both models and object classes supported by KITTI-trained models. Table 2 shows the impact of the PSA on the average detection confidence of these classes. Except for bikes, there is no systematic change in detection confidence visible for either of the evaluated object detection models, as they typically drive on the side of the road, which is not covered by the shifted FoV.

5.3.2 Camera

For the camera, we place a small piece of the DTF in front of a Sony IMX500 with a 12MP sensor [47], as depicted in Figure 7b, and capture videos at 30 frames per second (FPS). The DTF is placed to cause a right shift on the captured images. Additionally, we capture reference videos with a mobile phone camera without a perspective shift. With this

Table 2: Impact of the DTF-induced PSA on the average detection confidence for the LiDAR, using Pointpillars, and SECOND. Further limitations are discussed in Section 7.

Object	Pointpillars		SECOND	
	Benign	PSA	Benign	PSA
Car	68.39%	68.90%	70.60%	72.34%
Pedestrian	68.40%	60.50%	67.12%	63.93%
Bike	69.39%	0%	68.20%	63.92%

setup, we capture approximately 18 minutes of recordings that we use for our evaluation.

Figure 9 shows an overview of representative example images of this test drive. While the lanes and the drivable area are correctly segmented in their respective FoV, HybridNets [53] provides wrong coordinates in the attacked cases of Figure 9b. Especially, the direct neighboring lanes of the ego-vehicle in Figure 9a lead to the vanishing point in the optical center of the image. By contrast, the neighboring lanes of the right-shifted images from Figure 9b do not lead to the optical center of the image, but a vanishing point outside of the image on the left border. This observation is similar to the digitally simulated images of Figure 4. We emphasize that other models will lead to a similar result, since the PSAs do not attack the segmentation model but the FoV of the camera, as shown in Equations 5 and 6. Especially the incorrect segmentation of lanes and free space can lead to severe consequences in a fully autonomous vehicle, since cameras are typically the sole source of information for these tasks [21, 59].

To investigate the effect on object detection, we deploy Faster R-CNN [45], and an automotive-specific version of YOLOv10 [28] on both benign and attacked images. Similar to lane detection, these ML models are selected purely for being representatives of different model architectures, but the effect of our PSA is independent of the deployed model. While the detection threshold for Faster R-CNN is set to 0.8, it is 0.5 for YOLOv10. We investigate the following automotive-relevant object types for our evaluation: "Car," "Bicycle," "Person," "Motorcycle," "Bus," "Truck," and "Traffic Light." Table 3 shows the impact of the DTF-induced PSA on the average detection confidence of these classes. There is no systematic change in the detection confidence visible for either of the evaluated object detection models. While individual confidences, such as those for motorcycles, differ, they are the result of a low sample size in our recorded videos. Other object types that appeared more often in the test drive (e.g., cars) show no significant difference in confidence between the benign case and the attacked cases, but are incorrectly detected in position.

In addition to object detection, we evaluate the impact of PSAs on traffic sign detection, a task typically performed by cameras [21]. As previously described, we use YOLOv10,

(a) Representative benign images of the real-world tests, including detected lanes

(b) Representative right-shifted images of the real-world tests, including detected lanes

Figure 9: Overview of representative example images from our real-world tests. The images were captured in a real vehicle, and the lanes are detected through HybridNets [53]. While the lanes (green) and drivable area (orange) in the respective FoV are detected, their coordinates and direction differ. This can lead to misbehavior for AVs, especially for lane-keeping tasks.

Table 3: Average detection confidence for the camera, using Faster R-CNN, YOLOv10. While Faster R-CNN shows no significant difference, except for motorcycles, YOLOv10 shows a confidence decrease at objects that appeared less often. Further limitations are discussed in Section 7.

Object	Faster R-CNN		YOLOv10	
	Benign	PSA	Benign	PSA
Car	95.33%	95.10%	79.69%	78.30%
Bicycle	92.24%	94.50%	69.21%	83.49%
Person	93.66%	91.47%	78.34%	72.57%
Motorcycle	96.26%	85.81%	75.33%	69.78%
Bus	88.59%	91.81%	75.25%	68.74%
Truck	92.19%	88.40%	74.54%	74.41%
Traffic Light	94.69%	88.69%	69.63%	65.41%

specifically trained on the Mapillary dataset [12, 28]. As this model detects a wide range of traffic signs, we will focus on the most frequently detected traffic signs from the benign reference camera. While the adverse FoV change of our PSA may not be as relevant for this task, it is still important to avoid any negative impact on detection confidence, similar to object detection. As the results in Table 4 show, the detection confidence shows a slight reduction in the adverse case, but they are still detected with sufficient confidence. Especially traffic signs with unique shapes (e.g., "Yield") preserve their detection confidence, while less distinctive traffic signs (e.g., a 30km/h speed limit) show lower confidence.

Table 4: Impact of the DTF-induced PSA on the average camera-based traffic sign detection confidence for YOLOv10.

Sign	YOLOv10	
	Benign	PSA
Yield	83.94%	83.67%
Keep Right	83.94%	—*
Priority Road	80.78%	73.29%
Pedestrians Crossing	86.27%	69.82%
Roundabout	89.11%	77.21%
30km/h speed limit	87.34%	72.28%
No Entry	80.11%	88.28%

* Traffic Signs outside FoV

5.3.3 Multimodal

Besides the individual evaluation of the effects of PSAs on the LiDAR and the camera, we conduct real-world tests using both the previously mentioned front-facing Falcon Gen2 LiDAR [49] and the car's front-facing stereo camera, a Carnegie Robotics MultiSense S30 camera [7], simultaneously, mounted on top of a autonomous driving research vehicle, as shown in Figure 10

The deployment of our PSA on the LiDAR is the same as explained in Section 5.3.1. For the camera, we deploy the DTF in front of one of the image sensors of the stereo camera. This allows us to capture the benign reference image independently. For both sensors, we deploy our PSA to create

Figure 10: The sensor setup used for our multi-modal evaluation consists of a Falcon Gen2 LiDAR and a MultiSense S30 camera mounted on an autonomous driving research vehicle.

a left shift in the FoV. The goal of this analysis is the coherent deployment of PSAs in a multimodal sensor setup.

We evaluated the coherence of the attack in the multimodal setting by selecting a representative scene with many objects to be detected. This allows for visual inspection to observe the shift and its consequences on object detection.

As it is possible to see from Figure 11, both the LiDAR, in Figure 11a, and the camera, in Figure 11b, are under the effect of the left shift caused by the coherent PSA deployment. When comparing the results with our GT, the AV fails to detect objects that are present on the right side of the road. This confirms the success of our attack in the multimodal case, with detected objects from both sensors **exhibiting a coherent offset in their locations** and emphasizes the effectiveness of DTF-based PSAs against multi-sensor setups.

6 Attack Detection

The result of the multimodal analysis showed that the detection of PSAs must rely on OPSs themselves, and their captured data. Geometric consistency checks are ineffective because the transformation can be applied from the moment the AV starts, leaving no prior baseline for comparison. Instead, defenses must focus on physical artifacts introduced by the attack that subtly affect sensor behavior.

6.1 LiDAR

Under the threat model considered in this work, the adversary can shift the LiDAR FoV using a DTF. To classify whether a frame is under PSA manipulation, we propose a signal-level defense that exploits physical-layer artifacts observable in sensor data. An analysis of our LiDAR sensor reveals that when a DTF is applied to the LiDAR optics, the reflectivity signal undergoes a pronounced smoothing effect. Specifically, spatial regions that typically exhibit structured reflectivity distributions become significantly flattened. This observation provides a distinctive physical fingerprint of the attack: a salient high-frequency component. We further confirm this behavior

(a) LiDAR object detection with deployed DTF using Second

(b) Camera object detection with Faster-RCNN for both benign image (right) and deployed DTF (left)

Figure 11: Visual comparison of object detection for both camera and LiDAR. If PSAs are deployed coherently, the resulting detections are also coherent.

in the frequency domain. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the reflectivity signal shows a substantial suppression of high-frequency components in the presence of the DTF, consistent with the behavior of an optical low-pass filter. Based on this observation, we can set a cutoff frequency, in our case 0.1 (normalized spatial frequency), for the specific LiDAR model and monitor the magnitudes of spectral components exceeding this threshold. This cutoff is selected empirically; in our experiments, spectral magnitudes below this frequency remain largely comparable across benign and attacked signals, offering limited discriminatory power. However, for a different LiDAR, it might be necessary to evaluate which cutoff frequency works best, and analyze the false-positive ratio to avoid misdetection.

To quantitatively evaluate the proposed defense, we compute the *High-Frequency Energy Ratio* (HFR), defined as

$$\text{HFR} = \frac{|\mathcal{R}_{\text{cutoff}}|^2}{|\mathcal{R}_{\text{total}}|^2}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{\text{cutoff}}$ denotes the FFT coefficients whose spatial frequencies exceed the chosen cutoff, and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{total}}$ denotes the full reflectivity spectrum coefficients.

Figure 12: Fourier transform of the reflectivity sequences from two static laboratory scenes. The red plot corresponds to the case with the DTF applied, while the blue plot represents the baseline without the DTF. The low-frequency components are comparable across both cases and do not provide a strong discriminative feature for detecting the attack. In contrast, the high-frequency components exhibit a noticeable difference, indicating that high-frequency energy can serve as a strong feature for attack detection.

For benign scenes, we empirically estimate a threshold τ_{HFR} . At runtime, we apply the following decision rule: if the measured HFR falls below τ_{HFR} , the system flags the measurement as being under attack, indicating the presence of an adversarial optical filter.

6.2 Camera

Typically, automotive cameras capture parts of the ego vehicle within their FoV. Examples include the engine hood for front-facing cameras, as well as parts of the vehicle body and wheels for surround cameras. As these parts of images typically include unwanted reflections or distortions, they are usually removed [33]. We applied similar steps in our digital simulation: While the full-scale images in Figures 2d to 2f show large portions of the engine hood, the inference results in Figure 4 were cropped to avoid misdetections by unwanted reflections.

By contrast, such static ego-vehicle parts can serve as a basis for PSA detection. As the engine hood or other parts of the vehicle body remain stationary with respect to the camera position, their positions within captured images must always be similar. Semantic segmentation can be used to identify static portions of the ego vehicle. As PSAs affect the entire image, these stationary vehicle body parts will have a differently perceived position. Our proposed PSA detection for cameras, therefore, requires the full image from the sensor and must be applied before potential cropping.

To demonstrate the working principle of our proposed detection, we perform semantic segmentation on both the benign and attacked images in Figure 9. We use OneFormer as a state-of-the-art semantic segmentation model [23]. As shown in Figure 13, the shape of the detected ego vehicle engine hood (dark blue) differs significantly. For the benign images in Fig-

ure 13a, it shows the expected central part of the engine hood with slight curves, while the adversarially shifted images in Figure 13b have a clearly distinguishable edge, resulting from the now visible front right edge of the ego vehicle. To quantify this, we perform a quadratic fitting on the pixel values of the detected edge between the engine hood and other pixels, highlighted as a red line in Figure 13. There are two observations from the quadratic fit:

1. The adversarial images show the edge of the ego vehicle, **resulting in a lower quadratic coefficient**, as the quadratic fitting results in a downward-opening parabola.
2. Due to the changed FoV, the initial slope on the left side of the image is higher for adversarial images, compared to the benign ones, **resulting in a higher linear coefficient**.

These two parameters are static for benign images captured with a front-facing camera mounted statically and depend only on the exact vehicle model; for example, vehicles with a larger engine hood have different parameters. During vehicle development, manufacturers can integrate reference parameters into the camera for later use in identifying adversarial changes in the FoV. While our example is based on a front-facing camera and the engine hood, similar static vehicle parts can also be used for other camera placement options.

7 Limitations

We specifically investigated the adversarial effect on lane detection and odometry estimation, as well as a possible decrease in confidence for object and traffic sign detection. While humans can perceive artifacts in the captured data from both LiDAR and camera, our results in Tables 2 and 3 show that ML models show no systematic reduction in their confidence. While these artifacts are not a systematic drawback of PSAs, as our simulation shows, they are an effect of our specific DTF-based PSA, resulting from an optical film on OPSs.

Another limiting factor of DTF-based PSAs is the physical access that an attacker requires to place the film on the OPS. While the one-time physical access to the target vehicle is a limitation, it allows control of the target, not affecting unintended assets. Existing attacks require similar physical access in order to be deployed [17, 31, 50, 64].

For our evaluation, we considered a shift of 20° as per the commercial availability of the material. However, PSAs might be deployed with a different shift, and our digital simulation allows to examine different shifts and their effects on various algorithms.

8 Ethical Considerations

For the evaluation of our PSA, we use an autonomous driving research vehicle [26], operated in manual mode by a trained

Figure 13: Results of OneFormer semantic segmentation on the images of Figure 9. The red line shows a quadratic approximation of the engine hood. While the engine hood of the ego-vehicle, highlighted in dark blue, shows a slightly curved engine hood without strong edges in the benign case, it clearly shows the right edge of the ego-vehicle for the attacked images.

driver who maintained continuous control. This precaution ensured that human supervision was always present, thereby minimizing any potential risks to public safety. All data collection activities were conducted in low-traffic areas, in strict compliance with local traffic regulations, including applicable speed limits. The experiments were designed to avoid any hazardous driving behavior and did not interfere with other road users or public infrastructure. As our DTF-based PSA is manufacturer-agnostic, we did not perform responsible disclosure for specific sensor manufacturers.

9 Conclusion

In our work, we introduced PSAs as a novel class of attacks against LiDAR sensors and cameras used in AVs. Unlike prior physical adversarial attacks that aim to decrease the performance of perception algorithms, our approach operates by physically altering the sensing region itself via a DTF-induced perspective shift, thereby shifting the effective FoV with only minor adverse impact on the sensor operation. By providing a digital simulation of the effects for both LiDAR and camera, we enable the evaluation of an altered FoV on different algorithms.

For our evaluation, we specifically investigated the adversarial effect on lane detection and odometry estimation. Additionally, we show that PSAs result in no systematic change in confidence for object and traffic sign detection, however, their perceived location changes. Our evaluation is threefold: (i) *Digital Evaluation*: We evaluate the effect of a changed FoV using the KITTI odometry dataset for the LiDAR and

spherical images for the camera; (ii) *Static Physical Tests*: By performing physical tests in a controlled, static environment, we investigate the effect of the DTF to confirm its feasibility for a PSA, and (iii) *Real-World Tests*: We conduct extensive experiments with real vehicles to analyze the effect of the DTF-induced PSA in dynamic real-world scenarios, both for LiDAR and camera individually, as well as in a coherently applied multi-modal setup. The experimental results corroborate our central hypothesis: inducing systematic FoV shifts is sufficient to significantly degrade critical AV perception functionalities, even without injecting adversarial signals or modifying the environment.

By providing individual detection mechanisms for the LiDAR and camera, we aim to enhance the security of AVs. Our detection mechanisms work by solely receiving the sensor data and comparing it with a statistically derived threshold without the need for additional sensing hardware. While the detection mechanism for LiDAR is based on an intensity analysis of the received point clouds, our proposed mechanism relies on static reference points that are typically captured in vehicles, such as the engine hood.

Together, these results establish PSAs as previously unexplored, practically viable attacks for AVs, with significant implications for sensor security and perception robustness.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the European Union-funded projects CyberSecDome (Agreement No.: 101120779) and PANDORA (Agreement No.: 101135775).

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